

Magnetic Properties of MnAl Alloy with a β -phase

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Abstract

Designing new antiferromagnetic materials is a subject of interest due to their application in spintronic devices without having any stray fields [1-3]. The antiferromagnetic β phase of Mn-Al alloys were synthesized by arc melting followed by annealing. X-ray diffraction along with the Rietveld refinement suggested that these alloys crystallize in a β phase (Space group P4₁32). The electrical transport data provides an indication of semiconductor-like nature of the alloy. The behaviour of the β Mn-Al alloys was established from the temperature and field dependence magnetization measurement. Moreover, detailed analysis of magnetization data revealed the inhomogeneous magnetic disorder in the system with the coexistence of antiferromagnetic and a weak ferromagnetic phase. The strong spin fluctuations in this system lead to a large contribution of the electronic heat capacity [4], whereas the frequency dependent AC-Susceptibility data overruled the possibility of spin glass like behaviour in these alloys. Furthermore, the temperature variation of heat capacity was insensitive to the applied field of 3 Tesla with a negligible magnetic contribution.

Keywords: Intermetallics, Antiferromagnetism, Spintronics, Specific heat, β –Mn phase

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